

Speciation of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with maleic acid in CTAB-water mixtures

Gowri Kumari Vasireddy, Srinu Bogi, Nageswara Rao Choppa and B. B. V. Sailaja*

School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : sailaja_bbv@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received online 19 March 2016, accepted 28 March 2016

Abstract : Chemical speciation of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with maleic acid has been studied in varying concentrations (0.0–2.5% w/v) of CTAB-water mixtures maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ (NaCl) at 303 K. Stability constants of binary complexes were refined with the computer program MINIQUAD75. The best-fit chemical models were selected based on statistical parameters and residual analysis. The species detected are ML, ML₂ and ML₂H₂ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The trend in the variation of stability constants with change in mole fraction of the medium was explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. The species distribution diagrams and the plausible equilibria for the formation of the species are also presented.

Keywords : Speciation, binary complexes, maleic acid, computer modelling, CTAB, stability constants.

Introduction

Speciation study of essential metal ion complexes with maleic acid (MA) is useful to understand the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules. Chemical speciation of a molecule is governed by its structure and solvent effects^{1,2}. Hence in recent years researchers show interest in the study of metal ions interaction with various ligands^{3–5}.

MA is a dibasic unsaturated carboxylic acid, which is widely used in medicine, in the preparation of drugs, in agriculture as the plant growth regulators, in food industry and in plastic production⁶. MA is an industrial raw material for the production of glyoxylic acid by ozonolysis⁷. The maleate ion is the ionised form of MA. The maleate ion is useful in biochemistry as an inhibitor of transaminase reactions.

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) or cetrimonium bromide is a cationic surfactant. It is one of the components of topical antiseptic cetrimide. Its uses include providing a buffer solution for the extraction of DNA. Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are associated with several enzymes and any variation in their concentrations leads

to metabolic disorders⁸. Hence, the speciation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of MA in varying compositions of CTAB-water mixtures have been studied.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

0.05 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solution of MA (GR grade, E. Merck, Germany) was prepared by dissolving sample in water. To increase the solubility of ligand, 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration was maintained in the solution. GR samples of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, AR, Qualigens, India) was used as such and its purity was checked by determining critical micellar concentration (CMC) conductometrically. The CMC value of CTAB was 0.00093 mol L⁻¹ at 303 K. Solutions of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides (0.1 mol L⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ acid (HCl) to suppresses the hydrolysis of metal salts. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) pellets were used for the preparation of 0.40 mol L⁻¹ solution. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. Cobalt, nickel and copper chlorides were stan-

standardized using EDTA. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification⁹. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method¹⁰.

An ELICO (Model LI 120, India) pH meter of 0.01 readability (0–14 pH) in conjunction with a glass combination pH electrode was used. The pH meter was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.050 mol L⁻¹) in acidic region and borax (0.010 mol L⁻¹) in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated for several days in a well stirred CTAB-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. The effect of variations in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor¹¹.

Procedure :

All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying compositions of CTAB (0.0–2.5% w/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.160 mol L⁻¹ with sodium chloride at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. The electrode was equilibrated for 4–5 days in the required solvent system. For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with CTAB-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75, 1 : 5.0) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD¹² was used to calculate the correction factor. The binary stability constants were calculated from the pH metric titration data using the computer program, MINIQUAD75¹³. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and protonation constants of MA were fixed.

Results and discussion

Complex equilibria :

A preliminary investigation of alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of MA in the presence of mineral acid and inert electrolyte inferred that no condensed species are formed¹⁴. The best fit models were chosen as that with low standard deviation in the formation constants and minimum U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligands and hydrogen ion at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, which was corroborated by other statistical parameters like χ^2 , R -factor, skewness and kurtosis given in Table 1. The species detected for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions are ML, ML₂ and ML₂H₂.

A very low standard deviation in log β values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the model. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that most of the residuals are leptokurtic and a few form mesokurtic patterns. The values of skewness recorded in the tables are between -0.25 to 2.15. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R -value recorded.

Effect of micelles :

The variations in the magnitudes of the formation constants of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with MA in different compositions of the surfactant (CTAB) are shown in Fig. 1. The stabilities of binary complexes varied almost linearly with the mole fraction of the surfactant. This linear variation, due to the dielectric constant of the medium, decreases with increasing concentration of the surfactant^{15,16}. The non-linear variation

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of M(II)-MA complexes in CTAB-water medium

% w/v CTAB	log β_{mlh} (SD)			NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	χ^2	R-Factor	Kurtosis	pH-range
	ML	ML ₂	ML ₂ H ₂							
Co ^{II}										
0.0	4.56(15)	6.88(15)	17.76(07)	160	5.06	1.38	34.57	0.0091	8.43	1.5–8.0
0.5	6.17(13)	8.58(34)	18.47(37)	24	6.19	-0.11	1.78	0.0217	3.77	3.0–6.8
1.0	6.19(29)	8.57(21)	19.75(11)	21	5.33	-0.10	1.38	0.0155	2.32	2.2–8.0
1.5	5.94(13)	8.04(17)	18.21(16)	25	6.33	-0.15	2.33	0.0162	3.93	2.2–8.0
2.0	5.62(14)	8.52(34)	19.45(32)	73	10.56	-0.25	8.91	0.0227	3.24	2.0–8.0
2.5	5.96(23)	8.93(17)	19.90(15)	44	7.84	-0.16	7.39	0.0084	2.73	1.8–8.0
Ni ^{II}										
0.0	5.45(08)	7.42(26)	16.37(12)	104	5.06	0.54	46.26	0.0130	4.92	1.8–6.7
0.5	4.60(10)	7.90(22)	19.89(15)	35	10.48	-0.06	4.33	0.0107	3.36	2.5–7.2
1.0	6.17(25)	8.80(13)	20.39(19)	80	5.47	0.35	7.20	0.0215	4.26	2.3–7.0
1.5	6.62(27)	9.55(31)	20.99(29)	74	4.38	0.06	19.59	0.0085	3.54	2.3–7.0
2.0	4.80(13)	7.91(18)	18.61(10)	87	2.60	-0.02	8.17	0.0117	3.18	1.9–6.7
2.5	4.34(29)	7.42(14)	18.61(31)	46	9.99	-0.23	7.74	0.0233	2.41	1.9–6.7
Cu ^{II}										
0.0	4.98(05)	7.79(09)	15.80(14)	73	1.59	0.07	8.84	0.0088	3.43	2.0–5.9
0.5	5.90(25)	9.05(32)	19.19(25)	48	1.47	0.22	7.44	0.0146	3.14	2.9–7.0
1.0	5.28(43)	8.79(39)	19.40(29)	55	2.28	1.52	35.99	0.0249	7.71	2.9–7.4
1.5	4.46(29)	7.23(17)	19.65(20)	84	5.10	1.93	19.43	0.0133	9.67	2.3–7.9
2.0	4.67(32)	7.54(14)	19.98(12)	38	5.47	2.15	7.86	0.0102	5.29	2.4–8.0
2.5	4.86(17)	7.54(25)	20.06(22)	73	4.41	1.27	5.69	0.0095	4.57	2.4–7.9

$U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) \times 10^8$, where m = number of species; NP = Number of experimental points; SD = Standard deviation.

depends upon the polarity of the medium, charge on the micellar surface and on the non-electrostatic forces/hydrophobic interactions operating between the complex species and micellar surface. The species should be stabilized in the micellar medium with opposite charges due to electrostatic interactions but these charged species should be destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant of the medium. The stabilities of these species in CTAB-water medium do not show a particular trend because of the accumulation of metal ions and ligands on the surface of micelles with an increased concentration of surfactant and species with lower charge or high hydrophobicity are stabilized in the micellar pseudophase. This trend reflects in all M(II)-maleic acid complexes (Fig. 1).

Incorporation of errors :

In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experi-

mental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand and metal. The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > metal (Table 2). Some species were even rejected when errors are introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the appropriateness or correctness of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and the choice of the best fit models.

Distribution diagrams :

Some typical distribution diagrams of M(II)-MA in CTAB-water medium are shown in the Fig. 2. The different forms of MA are LH₂, LH⁻ and L²⁻ in the pH-

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of Co^{II}-MA complexes in 1.5% w/v CTAB-water medium

Ingredient	% Error	log β (SD)		
		ML	ML ₂	ML ₂ H ₂
Alkali	0	5.94(13)	8.04(18)	18.21(16)
	-5	Rejected	Rejected	17.47(41)
	-2	3.68(65)	Rejected	18.57(15)
	+2	6.40(39)	9.62(22)	Rejected
	+5	6.54(29)	12.31(54)	Rejected
Acid	-5	6.73(20)	11.95(42)	Rejected
	-2	6.35(34)	9.33(31)	Rejected
	+2	3.91(17)	8.34(43)	18.65(37)
	+5	2.17(38)	Rejected	17.40(33)
	-5	6.13(16)	9.00(23)	17.54(68)
Ligand	-2	6.04(15)	8.50(30)	17.95(27)
	+2	5.81(20)	7.44(29)	18.50(32)
	+5	4.41(22)	7.29(58)	19.17(26)
	-5	6.03(11)	8.29(38)	17.71(23)
	-2	5.97(12)	8.14(17)	18.08(16)
Metal	+2	5.90(13)	7.93(18)	18.31(16)
	+5	5.94(13)	8.12(17)	18.20(16)

range of 1.7–4.0, 1.7–6.5 and 4.5–6.5 respectively. The plausible binary metal-ligand species in different systems can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML, ML₂ and ML₂H₂ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The ML₂ species is the predominant species (Fig. 2) at higher pH and ML₂H₂ is the predominant species at lower pH among all the binary complexes. Low concentration of free metal ion (FM) indicates the strong complexing nature of MA. The formation of various binary complex species is shown in the following equilibria. Some typical distribution diagrams of CTAB-water media are shown in Fig. 2. Equilibria (1), (2) and (3) represent the formation of complexes from metal ion and the ligand. In alkalimetric titrations, protons are removed successively from the complexes by the addition of aliquots of the alkali. Equilibrium (4) represents the successive deprotonation of the complexes with increasing pH of the solution during alkalimetric titrations. Formation of ML₂ through the equilibria (4), (5) and (6) is proved by the increase in concentration of ML₂ by the decrease in concentration of ML and ML₂H₂. The forma-

Fig. 1. Variation of stability constant values of metal-MA complexes with mole fraction of CTAB-water mixtures : (A) Co^{II}, (B) Ni^{II}, (C) Cu^{II}; (■) log β_{ML}, (●) log β_{ML₂}, (▲) log β_{ML₂H₂}.

tion of various binary complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of MA complexes in 2.5% w/v CTAB-water medium : (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} and (C) Cu^{II} .

Structures of complexes :

In aqueous solutions metal ions are coordinated by six water molecules. Carboxylic acids replace water molecules and form metal-carboxylic acid complexes. Depending upon the nature of the ligands and metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge tentative structures of the complexes are proposed as shown in Fig. 3. Carboxyl oxygens of MA are bonded to the metal ions. The Cu^{II} ion forms distorted octahedral or square planar complexes due to Jahn-Teller effect.

Fig. 3. Structures of binary complexes of MA with $\text{M}(\text{II})$.

Conclusions

The present biomimetic studies of metal ion complexes with MA in CTAB-water mixtures indicate that the complexes are protonated in acidic pH values. The predominant species detected were ML , ML_2 and ML_2H_2 due to the interaction of MA with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} . These models are validated by statistical treatment of data. The linear or almost linear variation of $\log \beta$ values with the mole fraction of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces. Some species are stabilized due to electrostatic interactions and some are destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant. The order of reactants influencing the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors in their concentrations is alkali > acid > ligand > metal.

References

1. R. W. Taft, "Progress in Physical Organic Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1983, **14**, 247.
2. J. Hens, "Structural Effects on Equilibria in Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1975.
3. N. Vijaya Kumar, B. Sreekanth and G. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.*, 2012, **26**, 239.
4. Gowri Kumari Vasireddy, Nageswara Rao Choppa, Srinu Bogi and B. B. V. Sailaja, *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2015, **7**, 110.
5. V. S. Rao, P. S. Rao, B. Srikanth, C. K. Sastry and G. N.

- Rao, *Chem. Speciation and Bioavailab.*, 2009, **21**, 71.
6. S. A. Bychkova, A. V. Katrovtseva and E. V. Kozlovskii, *Russian Journal of Coordination Chemistry*, 2008, **34**, 172.
7. Kurt Lohbeck, Herbert Haferkorn, Werner Fuhrmann and Norbert Fedtke, "Maleic and Fumaric Acids", Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2000.
8. A. F. Kolodziej, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **41**, 493.
9. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005, 302.
10. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
11. B. B. V. Sailaja, T. Kebede, G. N. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 2004, **74**, 399.
12. G. N. Rao, PhD Thesis, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India, 1989.
13. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
14. G. N. Rao and S. B. Ronald, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 416.
15. A. K. Singh and D. Manjula, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 635.
16. E. H. Cordes, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 617.